

STATUS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AFTER NAAC ASSESSMENT AND ACCREDITATION

Mrs. Ipsita Patri

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Education, Rama Devi Women's University, BBSR

Dr. Sipra Ray

Asst. Professor in Education, SBWC, Cuttack

Paper Received On: 20 MAR 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 APRIL 2025

Published On: 01 MAY 2025

Abstract

Higher education plays vital role for creating knowledge and information based society. The mission and vision of higher education is to educate, train, and undertake research activities and service to the community. In such condition, it is necessary to have an effective and efficient quality assurance mechanism in our country. NAAC is a body established by the University Grants Commission of India to assess and accredit institutions of higher education in the country. The role of NAAC in ensuring the quality in defining the element of Higher Education in India through a combination of self and external quality evaluation, promotion and sustenance initiatives. To understand the procedures followed by NAAC, to evaluate quality of higher education institutions, to study how quality dimensions of higher education institutions have improved across different time periods will be addressed in this research topic. This topic stresses the perspectives of higher education in Indian educational development, NAAC and its efforts to bring quality in higher education.

Introduction

The Indian higher education system is one of the largest systems in the World. It is estimated that during the 11th Five Year Plan period, there will be a pressure on higher education system and a large number of additional students will be knocking at the doors of higher education institutions in the country. There are also new challenges of management and regulation being faced by higher education institutions, which require serious attention, both at the institutions in the public sector and also those in the private sector now growing at a fast pace. Besides, the demands of the society for equity and accommodation cannot be neglected any more. The core mission of higher education is to educate, train, undertake

Copyright © 2025, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

research and provide service to the community. Then to protect the quality of the higher education institutions, the National Policy Mission propose the Accreditation unit.

The number of higher educational institutions has been increasing rapidly for the past five decades. Some critics and educationists say that the country has allowed the mushrooming of private institutions offering fancy courses. Hence, the quality of education has been decreasing and education has become a market-centred product. The same opinion was also stressed by the National Policy on Education 1986 and it emphasised the deteriorating quality of higher education in the country. The Revised Education Policy (Plan of Action, 1992) spelt out the strategic plans for the policies and advocated the establishment of an independent national accreditation body to improve the quality of higher education in India. Thus, the NAAC was established as an outcome of the recommendations of New Education Policy (1986) and Revised Education Policy (1992) to uphold the quality of higher education. Based on this, University Grants Commission (UGC), under section 12 CCC of the UGC Act (Act 3 of 1956), established the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) as an Autonomous Institution on 16 September 1994 with Registered Office at Bangalore. The National Assessment and Accreditation Council are in its 29th year of operation now. It can certainly be a sufficiently long period for a National Quality Assurance Agency to take stock of its policies and practices. The two decades-old history of NAAC is a story of many triumphs and tribulations. Addressing the quality concerns of world's second largest higher education system has meant, adding several dimensions to the experiences of quality assurance initiatives of NAAC. Quality assurance models, as with higher education systems themselves, are designed to fulfil long- term collective needs. The quality assurance agencies are obliged to face enduring questions such as defining and maintaining standards of quality and equally important need to keep their methodologies up- to –date and responsive to shifting societal needs.

Higher education scenario in India

Quality in Higher Education has become a primary agenda of the countries worldwide. In the context marked by expansion of higher education and globalization of economic activities, education has become a national concern in developing countries with an international dimension. To cope with this changing context, developing countries have been pressurized to ensure and assure quality of higher education at a nationally comparable and internationally acceptable standard. Consequently, many developing countries such as India, China are initiated national quality assurance mechanisms and many more in the process of

Copyright © 2025, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

evolving a suitable strategy. But it's not going to be easy where there are resource constraints.

NAAC – An overview

To meet the quality aspect of current higher education system to attain international standards and excellence, quality assurance is the tool which is used by the government of India in recent years. The improvement for the run towards quality in all aspect in higher education cannot be achieved without the change in attitude and mind-set of and individual. Total quality management (TQM) which is consider as the 'Complete Food' with the synchronization of various tools and techniques, different methods of working in system, obeying the principles and incorporating harmoniously. The roadmap for quality management is control by the specified authority established by the University Grants Commission (UGC) in the name of National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC). NAAC enables the assurance of quality in higher education by involving all the stake holders from all the colleges in which ever universities they belong in every state of India. (Petare, 2016). The main motto of the NAAC for assessment and accreditation is to bring improvement and development in quality by ways of personal guideline, review by peer team members and self-imposed integrity in all domains of movement (Sahu, Shrivastava, & Shrivastava, 2013). Hence, with the support of NAAC, initiative should be taken for TQM movement in higher education. TQM is a process which is driven by a person and requires change in the person's attitude. It deals with continuous involvement of the process so as to bring out the best result from the stakeholders and also from the colleges and universities (Zabadi, 2013). The assessment of the universities and colleges for quality is based on the seven quality criteria including 33 Key Aspects in all for giving the accreditation of the college or the universities. Every five years the process of accreditation is assessed after the first cycle of accreditation so as to attain sustainability in quality in higher education. There are 1074 universities in India which includes Central Universities, Deemed Universities, State Universities, and Private Universities.

History of NAAC

NAAC was established in 1994 in response to recommendations of National Policy in Education (1986). This policy was to "address the issues of deterioration in quality of education", and the Programme of Action (POA-1992) laid out strategic plans for the policies including the establishment of an independent national accreditation body. Consequently, the NAAC was established in 1994 with its headquarters at Bengaluru.

NAAC Accreditation Process:

Any higher education institution from where two consequent batches have been graduated or who are in existence for last six years whichever is earlier, are considered eligible to apply for NAAC accreditation and assessment or fulfil the other conditions or are covered by other provisions, if any. NAAC accreditation does not cover distance education or offshore units of education. The institutions have to upload the data regarding the All India Higher Survey on Higher Education on AISHE portal; then they are provided with reference number which is an essential requirement for the institutions who are desirous to get registered for accreditation process. The NAAC assesses the quality of higher education institutions through an internationally accepted methodology which is guided by its vision and mission statements. NAAC changes its parameters for assessing the quality of higher education with the passage of time. Earlier accreditation process was offline now it is totally e-process or digitized process. These changes also reflect the example of quality education and innovation. NAAC assesses and grades institutions through three step process instrument.

- Preparation for the self-study report by institution or department based on parameters defined by NAAC.
- Validation of the Self-study report by a team of peers through onsite visit; presentation of the detailed quality report to the institution.
- Final decision on assessment and accreditation by National Assessment and Accreditation Council.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the status of NAAC accredited Autonomous Colleges with reference to the 7 aspects of NAAC.
2. To study the opinion of stakeholders viz. students and teachers of higher education institutions with respect to status after NAAC assessment and accreditation.

Research question

1. What is the status of NAAC accredited Autonomous Colleges with reference to the 7 aspects of NAAC?
2. What are the opinion of stakeholders' viz. students and teachers of higher education institutions with respect to status after NAAC assessment and accreditation?

Methodology

The design is survey with selection of sample from 2 autonomous colleges (B.B. Autonomous college and V.N. Autonomous college) of Jajpur District affiliated to Utkal University. The study was designed to find out the status after NAAC accreditation in selected colleges. Investigator herself developed tools for the purpose of data collection. In the present study the investigator selected 100 students, 30 Teachers as a sample from 2 Colleges of the Utkal University. The sampling was done with convenient sampling technique. For this purpose, the researcher has prepared following set of tools and these were used by the researcher in order to collect adequate, relevant and accurate information.

1. Questionnaire for teachers (Self developed tool)
2. Opinionnaire for students (Self developed tool)

Administration and scoring of the tools resulted in enormous data and the investigator was processed and analysed this data by adopting percentage wise analysis.

Student's opinion

Table No.-1: overall responses received for seven criteria of NAAC

Criteria	Positive responses	N
Curricular aspects	91 (91%)	100
Teaching, learning and evaluation	92 (92%)	100
Research, Consultancy and Extension	85 (85%)	100
Infrastructure and Learning Resources	94 (94%)	100
Student Support and Progression	91 (91%)	100
Governance, Leadership and Management	92 (92%)	100
Innovations and Best Practices	95 (95%)	100

Teacher's Opinion:-

Table No.-2: overall responses received for seven criteria of NAAC

Criteria	Positive response	N
Curricular Aspects	27 (90%)	30
Teaching-Learning and Evaluation	27 (91%)	30
Research, Consultancy and Extension	24 (81%)	30
Infrastructure and Learning Resources	28 (95%)	30
Student Support and Progression	27 (90%)	30
Governance, Leadership and Management	27 (92%)	30
Innovations and Best Practices	28 (96 %)	30

Findings

1. If we take teacher's opinion regarding NAAC criterion-wise analysis, the highest percentage of positive response of 96% is received for Criteria-7: Institutional values and Best Practices. Second highest is 95% for Criteria-4: Infrastructure and Learning Resources and third highest is 92% for Criteria-6: Governance Leadership and Management followed by 91% for Criteria-2: Teaching, Learning and Evaluation,

90% for Criteria-5: Student Support and Progression, 90% for Criteria-1: Curricular Aspect and 81% for Criteria-3: Research, Innovation and Extension.

2. If we take student's opinion regarding NAAC criterion-wise analysis, the highest percentage of positive response of 95% is received for Criteria-7: Institutional values and Best Practices. Second highest is 95% for Criteria-4: Infrastructure and Learning Resources and third highest is 92% for Criteria-6: Governance Leadership and Management followed by 92% for Criteria-2: Teaching, Learning and Evaluation, 91% for Criteria-5: Student Support and Progression, 91% for Criteria-1: Curricular Aspect and 85% for Criteria-3: Research, Innovation and Extension.

Conclusion

From this study, it is very clear that, HEIs in the country are highly benefitted by the NAAC accreditation in terms of improving their quality at their respective institutions. It is evident that the overall quality improvement of the HEIs is depending directly on NAAC seven criteria and its 34 key indicators. From this we can conclude that, in order to provide quality education, the institutions need to adopt quality initiatives in terms of curriculum design, infrastructure, strengthening of research activities, IT reforms, examination reforms, student satisfaction and feedback etc. In order to achieve this goal, external assessment by the agency like NAAC is very important. Hence, there is a high impact of NAAC Accreditation on the higher education institutions of the country. Similarly, the respective governments should provide necessary fund allocations and other facilities to all the HEIs and should encourage them to undergo NAAC accreditation compulsorily.

REFERENCES

- Aithal, P.S., & Aithal, S. (2021). *A comparative study on research performance of Indian Universities with NAAC A++ grade accreditation. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 254-285.
- Chakrabarti, P. (2015). *Evaluation of performance of Internal Quality Assurance Cells (IQACs) of selected NAAC accredited General Degree colleges affiliated to the University of Calcutta. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/172633>*
- CL, N., & Kannappannavar, B.U. (2020). *Impact of NAAC assessment on the development of college libraries: A study. Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 4190. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4190>
- K, R., Samanta, S., & Rath, A.K. (2021). *Impact of NAAC accreditation on quality improvement of Higher Education Institutions in India: A Case Study in the State of Karnataka. Empirical Research Paper*, 14(1), 35-49. <http://naac.gov.in/images/docs/Key-Indicators-and-Weightages.pdf>